
THE ROLE OF PARODY IN POSTMODERN LITERATURE

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Annotation: Parody plays a vital role in postmodern literature, serving as both a tool for critique and a means of creative reinvention. This article examines the multifaceted functions of parody, including its capacity to deconstruct established norms, challenge canonical texts, and critique cultural ideologies. Rooted in a tradition of literary imitation, postmodern parody moves beyond simple satire to blend homage with subversion, often employing intertextuality and playfulness to disrupt readers' expectations. Through examples such as Thomas Pynchon's *The Crying of Lot 49* and Margaret Atwood's *The Penelopiad*, the essay highlights how parody destabilizes authority and invites new interpretations of traditional narratives

.Key words: vocabulary parody moves, developmental stages, receptive language, canonical texts

Аннотация: Пародия играет важную роль в постмодернистской литературе, служа как инструментом критики, так и средством творческого переосмысления. В статье рассматриваются многоаспектные функции пародии, включая её способность деконструировать установленные нормы, бросать вызов каноническим текстам и критиковать культурные идеологии. Уходя корнями в традиции литературного подражания, постмодернистская пародия выходит за рамки простой сатиры, сочетая дань уважения с подрывом основ, часто используя интертекстуальность и игровую манеру для разрушения ожиданий читателей. На примерах таких произведений, как «Выкрики лота 49» Томаса Пинчона и «Пенелопада» Маргарет Этвуд, подчеркивается, как пародия дестабилизирует авторитет и предлагает новые интерпретации традиционных нарративов.

Ключевые слова: пародия, этапы развития, рецептивный язык, канонические тексты.

Introduction:

Parody, a form of imitation that often employs satire, humor, and exaggeration, plays a significant role in postmodern literature. This literary device serves not only as a tool for critique and commentary but also as a means of deconstructing established norms and conventions. In the fragmented and self-referential world of postmodernism, parody emerges as a way to question authority, subvert traditional narratives, and challenge readers' expectations. This essay explores the multifaceted role of parody in postmodern literature, examining its functions, implications, and contributions to the broader discourse of literary and cultural criticism. Parody has a long-standing history in literature, dating back to ancient Greece, where Aristophanes parodied societal norms through comedic plays. In the Middle Ages, works such as Chaucer's *The Canterbury Tales* often utilized parody to critique societal and religious institutions. However, the postmodern era marks a distinctive turn in the use of parody. No longer confined to mere humor or critique, parody in postmodernism becomes a vehicle for profound cultural and philosophical questioning.

Postmodern parody, as defined by theorists such as Linda Hutcheon, moves beyond simple imitation or ridicule. It involves the conscious reworking of existing texts to create something new while retaining the recognizable framework of the original. This duality—simultaneously paying homage to and undermining the original—highlights the playful yet critical nature of postmodern parody. One of the key roles of parody in postmodern literature is its function as a deconstructive tool. By mimicking and altering canonical works or established genres, parody exposes their underlying assumptions and ideological biases. For example, in Thomas Pynchon's *The Crying of Lot 49*, the parody of detective fiction not only lampoons the genre's tropes but also questions the possibility of objective truth and coherent narratives. Similarly, Margaret Atwood's *The Penelopiad* parodies Homer's *The Odyssey* by retelling the story from Penelope's perspective. This subversive

reimagining critiques the patriarchal lens of the original text, highlighting the marginalization of female voices in classical literature. By deconstructing revered works, parody in postmodernism disrupts the perceived sanctity of literary canon and invites readers to reconsider dominant cultural narratives.

Parody in postmodern literature often exemplifies the era's obsession with playfulness and intertextuality. Postmodern works frequently reference, reinterpret, or even rewrite earlier texts, creating a web of interconnected narratives. This self-referential approach underscores the belief that literature is inherently interdependent, and meaning is constructed through the interplay of texts. Consider Italo Calvino's *If on a Winter's Night a Traveler*, which parodies the act of reading itself. The novel continually shifts between beginnings of stories, poking fun at the reader's desire for narrative closure while exploring the nature of storytelling. The playful tone invites readers to engage with the text on multiple levels, blurring the lines between author, reader, and story. Moreover, intertextual parody often serves to democratize literature by incorporating diverse influences, ranging from highbrow classics to popular culture. Salman Rushdie's *The Satanic Verses* exemplifies this synthesis, parodying religious texts, modernist literature, and Bollywood tropes. By juxtaposing disparate elements, Rushdie creates a rich tapestry of meanings that defy singular interpretation.

Beyond its literary functions, parody in postmodern literature often acts as a lens for cultural and political critique. By mimicking societal norms and values, parody can expose hypocrisies and contradictions within prevailing ideologies. Kurt Vonnegut's *Slaughterhouse-Five* is a prime example. The novel parodies traditional war narratives, replacing glorified depictions of heroism with absurdist humor and fatalistic resignation. Through this parody, Vonnegut critiques the romanticization of war and challenges readers to confront its senseless brutality. The novel uses humor and exaggeration to subvert traditional moral authority, advocating for personal freedom and self-discovery.

While parody in postmodern literature is often celebrated for its critical insights, it is not without its controversies. The dual nature of parody—

simultaneously critiquing and celebrating its source—can sometimes blur the line between subversion and complicity. Critics argue that certain parodic works risk reinforcing the very structures they seek to undermine by drawing attention to them without offering meaningful alternatives. For instance, Bret Easton Ellis's *American Psycho* parodies consumer culture and toxic masculinity through its hyperbolic depictions of violence and materialism. However, some readers have questioned whether the novel's graphic content crosses into sensationalism, overshadowing its critique. This tension underscores the complexity of parody as a literary device and its potential for misinterpretation. As literature continues to evolve in the digital age, the role of parody expands beyond traditional texts to encompass multimedia platforms. Memes, fan fiction, and remix culture are contemporary forms of parody that align with postmodern principles of intertextuality and fragmentation. These modern parodies democratize literary creation, allowing individuals to participate in the reinterpretation of cultural artifacts. For example, fan fiction often parodies popular works by reimagining characters or plots in unconventional ways, challenging authorial authority and exploring alternative narratives. Similarly, internet memes, though brief and often comedic, can serve as potent vehicles for social and political critique, embodying the postmodern ethos of subversion and play.

Parody occupies a central role in postmodern literature, functioning as a tool for deconstruction, cultural critique, and creative reinvention. By reworking existing texts and genres, postmodern parody challenges traditional notions of authorship, originality, and authority. Its playful yet critical nature reflects the broader postmodern preoccupation with ambiguity, intertextuality, and fragmentation. While parody's duality can lead to interpretive challenges, it remains a powerful means of questioning and reshaping cultural narratives. In an era characterized by rapid change and shifting identities, parody continues to resonate as a dynamic and relevant form of expression, bridging the past and present while pointing toward the possibilities of the future.

REFERENCES

1. **Hutcheon, Linda.** *A Theory of Parody: The Teachings of Twentieth-Century Art Forms.* New York: Methuen, 1985.
2. **Pynchon, Thomas.** *The Crying of Lot 49.* Philadelphia: J.B. Lippincott & Co., 1966.
3. **Atwood, Margaret.** *The Penelopiad.* Edinburgh: Canongate Books, 2005.
4. **Vonnegut, Kurt.** *Slaughterhouse-Five.* New York: Delacorte Press, 1969.
5. **Calvino, Italo.** *If on a Winter's Night a Traveler.* New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, 1979.
6. **Jameson, Fredric.** *Postmodernism, or, The Cultural Logic of Late Capitalism.* Durham: Duke University Press, 1991.